

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

THEORETICAL BASICS OF ACCOUNTING SUPPORT FOR FINANCIAL PLANNING OF ENTERPRISE ACTIVITIES

Fatenok-Tkachuk A.,

Lesya Ukrainka Volyn National University, Lutsk,

Ph.D., Associate Professor, Associate Professor of Accounting and Taxation

Sadovska I.,

Lesya Ukrainka Volyn National University, Lutsk,

Doctor of Economics, Professor, Head of Department Accounting and Taxation

Yanush R.

Lesya Ukrainka Volyn National University, Lutsk,

Master of Accounting and Taxation

Abstract

The theoretical foundations of financial planning of enterprise activity as an element of management process are presented. The functions of financial planning are allocated. The characteristic features of individual components of the system of functional budgets at the enterprise are grouped. The stages of financial planning and their content for the purpose of effective management are given.

Keywords: Accounting, financial planning, budgeting, financial flows.

Financial planning is considered the basis of the organization of the enterprise's finances, because it provides for an economic substantiation of the volume of revenues and directions of spending funds, as well as the volume of formation of monetary assets necessary for the continuous functioning of the enterprise. Business entities are interested in a real assessment of their financial situation today and in the near future, not only to succeed in their entrepreneurial activities, but also to timely fulfill their obligations to the budget, social funds, banks and other creditors. Therefore, it is important to calculate income and expenses in advance, take into account the consequences of inflation, changes in the market situation, violations of contractual obligations by partners. This is especially important in wartime.

Financial planning is an element of the overall planning process, and is also the basis and responsible component of the functional management system. It allows you to identify bottlenecks in the enterprise's economic activity.

As a type of activity, financial planning is such an activity that is aimed at maximizing the efficiency of the functioning of enterprises, as well as solving the tasks set. The definition of financial planning as a document has a double content due to the presence of several groups of financing objects: Resources, i.e. assets and liabilities, and transactions that form the system of financial relations^[2].

The goal of financial planning in practice should be to justify the need for capital to ensure the forecasted volumes of operating and investment activities, coordination with the capital that can actually be attracted, resource support for the circulation of production funds on the basis of financial stability, solvency, creation of prerequisites for obtaining profit in the amount, sufficient for economic and social development^[3].

In the process of financial planning, the business

entity evaluates the state of its finances from various points of view, the possibility of growth of financial resources and the efficiency of their use. In most cases, the managers of the enterprise make management decisions during planning based on the analysis of financial information. According to this, scientists distinguish the following main functions of financial planning: reduction of complexity; motivation; prognostication; security; optimization; coordination and integration; ordering; control; documentation; training^[4].

It is known that the main goal of the enterprise is to maximize profits while simultaneously reducing costs. Since effective distribution of financial resources can contribute to achieving this, it is necessary for financial planning^[3]:

- to determine the amount of necessary and realistically possible monetary resources according to the sources of their formation and directions of use for the implementation of operational, investment and other types of activities;

- to optimize the capital structure by sources and directions of placement;

- to determine the projected profitability of the capital advanced for the formation of the company's assets;

- to develop alternative or preventive measures in case of deviations from the predicted indicators;

- monitor and respond promptly to the progress of the implementation of the financial plan.

This process should also be carried out in stages, namely in terms of: income, expenses, profit from operating, investment, financial and other types of activities, net profit and directions of its use; working capital needs by sources and directions of use; sources of investment resources for the implementation of the capital investment plan; amount and directions of use of social funds; balance of assets and liabilities at the end of the planned period^[5].

Accordingly, five stages of financial planning are distinguished. The first is to develop a plan of income, expenses and profit in order to make sure that the net profit is sufficient for self-sufficiency.

The second stage is special because here it is necessary to ensure an uninterrupted cycle of production and circulation funds with the help of a sufficient amount of money resources, which is appropriate to make up the balance of money resources.

The third stage is related to the determination of sources of funding for capital investments in order to avoid deficits in financing objects and to prevent unplanned withdrawal of own funds from circulation for capital investments^[2].

The social policy of the financial planning process should also not be forgotten, which is why the next stage belongs. After all, in order to ensure the successful implementation of the indicators of the financial plan, it is necessary to pay due attention to the company's personnel and its social security, since material incentives are an important motivation for work and innovation, which corresponds to the Sustainable Development Goals.

As for the final stage, it is necessary not only to draw up a forecast balance of assets and liabilities of the enterprise, but also to determine what kind of structural changes will take place under the conditions of the implementation of the financial plan. It is also necessary to assess their impact on the financial condition of the enterprise based on forecast calculations of expected indicators, which are used to assess financial stability. And, of course, for an adequate assessment of the effectiveness of financial planning, it is necessary to conduct a comparative analysis of indicators for peri-

ods from three to five years in order to prevent a possible deterioration of the company's financial condition.

The financial plan will contain background information on the actual indicators of the past year and the planned indicators of the current year. The business entity has the opportunity to draw up a financial plan and prepare an explanatory note using the recommendations for drawing up the enterprise's financial plan and a report on its implementation. In addition to regulatory legal acts, the enterprise can also independently develop various internal instructions, methodological recommendations for regulation and improvement of the financial planning process.

The system of financial plans (budgets) of Western corporations includes: a forecast of the balance of assets and liabilities; profit and loss statement forecast; cash flow statement forecast; forecast of key financial indicators (sales volume, production and circulation costs, profit, return on assets and equity, share price, etc.); long-term budget of capital investments and assessment of investment projects; the long-term financing strategy of the corporation^[6].

The experience of the countries with market economy shows that with the growth of the level of financial planning, the efficiency of enterprise management increases. Foreign economic entities carry out financial planning, usually within the framework of various management systems: budgeting, controlling and balanced scorecard.

In order to organize the budget planning of the activity of structural units of the enterprise, it is advisable to create an end-to-end system of budgets at the enterprise, consisting of several functional budgets (Table 1.). This system of budgets includes the entire base of financial calculations.

Table 1.

Characteristics of the system of functional budgets in the enterprise

Type of functional budget	Characteristics
The budget of the wage fund	With the budget of the wage fund, related to payments to extrabudgetary funds (pension, social insurance, employment) and parts of tax deductions.
Budget of material costs	Budgets of material costs and energy consumption reflect the main part of third-party payments of the enterprise
Energy consumption budget	
Amortization budget	The depreciation budget is largely for the purpose of the enterprise's investment policy, in addition, depreciation deductions can be used as working capital of the enterprise
Budget of other expenses	The budget of other expenses will allow you to save on the least important financial expenses.
Loan repayment budget	The loan repayment budget and the position to make loan and loan repayment operations in strict accordance with the payment schedule plan
Tax budget	The additional budget includes all taxes and mandatory payments to the state budget and budgets of other levels, as well as to extrabudgetary funds (pension fund, social insurance fund, health insurance, employment, etc.). This budget is planned only for the enterprise as a whole.

At the same time, foreign enterprises, when creating budgets of structural divisions and relevant services, always ensure that each lower-level budget is a detail of a higher-level budget, that is, production budgets specify a consolidated (complex) budget.

In order to determine which accounting procedures the accountant performs at each of the stages of financial planning, we will list the stages that this multi-stage process includes: analysis of financial indicators for past periods; development of financial strategy and financial policy; drawing up current financial plans; coordination of financial plans with production, commercial, investment and other plans and programs of the enterprise; operational financial planning; analysis and control of execution of plans.

At the first stage, financial indicators of the company's activity for the previous period are analyzed. The source of information support for this process is financial reporting and accounting registers. On the basis of the conducted analysis, the enterprise can assess the financial results of its activities and the placement of the problems that arise before it.

At the second stage of financial planning, a financial strategy is developed and the foundations of financial policy are laid^[2]. The development of a financial strategy has a certain sequence of actions: analysis of the factors of the external and internal environment of the enterprise; development of a system of strategic

goals; determination of possible options for the company's financial strategy; formation of a financial strategy; financial strategy implementation; financial strategy monitoring; detection of deviations, correction of the chosen strategy or activity of the enterprise itself^[4].

As for the third stage, here the main indicators of the forecast financial documents are specified and specified with the help of drawing up current financial plans. The current financial plan is a plan of income and expenses for the current year, which ensures a certain level of profitability of the enterprise, as well as sources of formation and directions of receiving funds.

Current financial plans are developed in terms of such financial plans as: income and expenses from operational, financial and investment activities; receipts and expenditures of funds; balance of monetary resources; cash resources plan for financing current assets; investment plan.

The purpose of the first plan is to determine the amount of net profit from the economic activity of the enterprise by means of forecasting the indicators of income and expenses (Fig. 1.).

The cash receipts and disbursements plan is a plan, the main task of which is to determine the amount and need for cash of various forms for the implementation of planned operating expenses and investment programs, as well as to ensure the receipt of these resources in the process of carrying out economic activities by the economic entity.

Fig. 1. Forecast indicators of the income and expenditure plan from operational, financial and investment activities

Drawing up such a current plan will allow to control the ensuring of permanent solvency of the enterprise at all stages of the planned period and provides for the implementation of concretization of the carrying out (planning) of the relevant indicators of receipts and expenditures of funds

An important problem of financial planning is to ensure the validity of the financial plan, its reality. By paying more attention to financial planning, it is possible to strengthen the financial stability of the enterprise, provided that the volumes of operating and investment activities predicted by the business plan are fulfilled on the basis of financial stability, and the creation of prerequisites for obtaining a net profit sufficient for self-sufficiency and self-financing of the enterprise.

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